

THE EROSION PHENOMENA AFFECTING RESIDUAL STRESS IN NICKEL CHROMIUM ALLOYED IRONS

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ABSTRACT

The nickel chromium alloyed irons find extensive applications in industries especially in thermal power plants as wear resistant materials. Also, it is known that failure of any part may occur due to fatigue, erosion, creep, wear related problems. Many researchers have reported the cause of failures, which are attributed to thermal degradation, chemical attack, residual stress built up, higher operating speed etc. In this regard, the influence of high temperature, corrosion and other process parameters influencing residual stress in metallic materials have been addressed, documented and published, but the information on wear damage assessment in metals especially white irons affecting residual stress is less reported. Considering all the above aspects in view, the present work provides an insight in to residual stress development due to erosive wear in nickel chromium irons coupled with other associated findings such as composition, hardness, microstructure and roughness supporting the stress profile.

1. Introduction

It is well known that residual stresses get originated in any engineering component on account of various manufacturing and their intermediate processes encountered by them. The residual stresses are the ones that remain in body even after the external force is removed and they get formed due to occurrence of plastic deformation. Even the onset of various types of damages that take place in a component may contribute to significant level of residual stress generation. Although several studies have been addressed with regard to the interactions of fatigue, creep, corrosion, embrittlement on the residual stress but the wear profile affecting the stress is less explored. The proposed investigation would give very good information and insight into the type of wear damage, mechanisms and its effect on residual stress and implications thereof.

Now the literature review points with regard to the origin of residual stress affected due to mechanical/chemical /high temperature damages are considered for discussion. In a work conducted by Diana et al [1] on the fatigue life affected due to surface residual stress in AL 356 alloy, the measurements and evaluation of residual stress due to different loading conditions for

no of cycles to failure and critical flaw sizes of a component with varied geometry have been reported. Further the use of AFGROW module to predict the fatigue life for varied mechanical loads and simulation carried out to for arrive at fatigue crack growth rate and fracture toughness data have been addressed. The AFGROW program mainly concentrated on life predictions (no of cycles to failure) based on failure modes, critical flaw type, size and location, applied load, stress ratio, residual stress levels etc. It is enumerated in their work [2] that nondestructive method is appropriate to determine residual stress on the surface and sub surface to arrive at its magnitude and distribution aspects. Thus in summary NDT methods of stress analysis has been adopted for the advantage of predicting residual stress in Al alloys. May Phyoaung et al [3] have effectively studied the influence of residual stress generated during induction heating of structural steel plates on tentative behaviour. As reported in the work, 12mm thick stress plates with induction heating carried out at 250°C and 350° C by considering them as case 1 and case 2, respectively. with heat treatment cycles involving single and double thermal cycling. The performance of the plate with double heating up to 350°C has been reported to be favourable by super imposing tensile on compressive stress. Further, the numerical simulation involving double heating has resulted in getting uniform thermal efficiency. The study has provided better fatigue performance of the welded plates. Further, it has given very good impetus to the onset of favourable residual stresses in structural plates due to the thermal load application. Another work conducted by Asbari mousavi and Mirosmaelli[4] have reported on the on set of residual stress and its distribution in weldments involving both plastic and thermal strains. It is reported in their work regarding the influence of mechanical constraints in the U and V grooved weldments to arrive at the effect of groove configuration on the residual stress levels. Based on this study the grove configuration has been operationalized.

In a literature review dealing with the influence of residual stress on fatigue strength of steels, it is reported that fatigue properties are complex in nature and they have bearing on the stress levels induced. As reported[5,6] that the parameters like roughness, hardness, corrosion, wear, temperature play vital role in bringing down the fatigue properties and Vice versa. Also, dealt with fatigue failures attributed to the generation of tensile stresses and required further attention from the point of controlling the residual stresses due to the various damages taking place in materials especially in corrosion and wear situations.

Now coming to the literature aspects on the wear is respect aspects of the advanced coatings influencing residual stress are considered for discussion, Andrew velvet et al [7] in their work came out with hard metal coatings WC-10VC-12Co produced by HVOF method done on mild steel substrate. As reported they were assessed for slurry erosion and its influence on residual stress in the eroded regions from the point of obtaining better mechanical integrity. The study conducted has been proved to be useful from the point of superior slurry erosion resistance together with onset of high compressive stress on the erosion scars. Philip oladijo et al [8] studied the influence of residual stress of WC 17Co HVOF coatings done on different substrates viz. Aluminum alloy, SS304, brass and super invar. The stress determined by XRD techniques showed compressive

stresses and the reason getting such trends have been reported to be due to type of stresses generated on account of the differences in the coefficient of thermal expansion between the coating and the substrate. High macroscopic residual stress in PVD coatings to predict the performance of tools was reported by H Oettel and R Wiedemann [9] in respect of thermo elastic effect and growth in defects due to the fast deposition of powder during the coating process. Tommi Varies et al [10] studied the WC-CoCr dense coatings using the advanced HVOF and HVOF methods. An accumulation of residual stress has been reported by super position of thermal mismatch, quenching and peening stresses. It is stated in their work regarding the tolerant coating design for the wear performance to resist cavitation and abrasion to establish relationship between wear and residual stress with high compressive stresses getting developed.

The above discussion pertaining to residual stress build up due to wear damage in coatings and also its effect due to induction heating and fatigue associated problems, but the wear damage especially erosion in materials affecting residual stress need to be explored as the literature aspects on this is very meagre and hence requires an in-depth study. Keeping this aspect in view, the work presents the development of residual stress due to erosion phenomena and its influence on hardness, microstructure and retained austenite to evolve correlations among them.

2.0 Experimental Procedure

The experimental procedure consists of materials and methods as detailed below.

2.1 Materials

The materials considered for the assessment of erosion damage affecting residual stresses are Ni Hard 4 Iron, High chromium iron, and High chromium Manganese iron castings having dimensions $150 \times 150 \times 10 \text{ mm}^3$ produced by induction melting technique. For cross comparison Mild steel in the cold rolled condition has been employed in this study.

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Melting and Casting.

The castings were prepared by the melting route using a coreless type induction furnace of 15kW. Capacity operation at 9.6 kHz. The test samples were produced in a gray cast iron metal mould having the dimensions $150 \times 150 \times 25 \text{ mm}^3$. To strip the casting from mould, acetylene suit was provided to the inner parts of the metal mould. The use of metal mould has distinct advantages of getting good surface finish, less environmental pollution and improved dimensional stability. The test samples having the dimensions $75 \times 25 \times 5 \text{ mm}^3$ were prepared by cutting and grinding operations to carry out the tests.

2.2.2 Chemistry

The chemical composition of the samples was analysed using optical emission spectrophotometer as per JIS a 1253-2013 standard.

2.2.3 Heat Treatment

The Nickel chromium iron samples have been heat treated as per the details given below.

- (a) The Ni hard 4 was subjected to destabilization treatment at 820°C for 4 hours followed by air cooling, subsequently sub critical was given at 350°C .

- (b) High chromium iron samples are austenized at 950⁰C, soaked for 6hours, then quenched in oil followed by tempering treatment at 200⁰C for about half an hour and subsequently air cooled.
- (c) High chromium manganese iron samples are austenized at 950⁰C, soaked for 6 hours, then quenched in oil followed by tempering treatment at 200⁰C for about half an hour and air cooled.

2.2.4 Hardness

The hardness measurement have been done on the test samples using Rockwell hardness C tester at a load of 150kg with diamond cone indenter. The tests are carried at accordance with ASTM standard.

2.2.6 Microstructure

The light micrographs of the samples have been examined using metallurgical microscope at magnification of X500, The sample preparation for microstructure was done involving polishing using SIC emery paper of grit size 200,400,600 and 800 followed by cloth polishing involving diamond paste, kerosene etc. The sample is then etched using the **nital** solution. (3% nitric acid (NH₃) and 97% ethanol)

2.2.7 Erosion

The erosion tests have been conducted in a high mass flux regime erosion tester. The guideline followed for erosion test are from the ASTM standard G 76 [11]

The parameters employed during the tests selected were 15⁰,30⁰,45⁰,60⁰ and 90⁰

- (1) Abrasive silica sand (AFS 60)
- (2) Impact angle 45⁰, 90⁰
- (3) Particle flow-600 to 700gm/min
- (4) Particle Velocity 35m/s
- (5) Nozzle diameter 5mm
- (6) Test duration: 30 s

The erosion test process masses use of compressed air free from moisture and oil mixed with silica sand abrasive particles (AFS 60 grade) and made to impinge on the target sample using a ceramic nozzle having diameter of 5 mm and time interval of 30 seconds. An electronic high precession digital balance is used to measure the initial weight of the samples. At the end of the test, the sample is cleaned, and the final weight is measured using the same balance. The erosion loss measured is the weight difference between the initial and final weight readings of the samples. For each erosion test three tests were made and the average value has been reported, the coefficient values (CV) have been arrived at based on the measurement providing standard deviation and the no of sizes, as per the ASTM standard, The CV should lie below 17%. In this present experiments also, the CV obtained is less than 5%.

2.2.8 X-Ray tests

The main purpose of this test is to measure the residual stress and retained austinite of the cast samples under investigation. The residual stress measurements were done on the test samples using

X-Ray deflection XRD method (Rigaku X-Ray stress Analysis) according to the ASTM Standard [12]. The X-Ray radiation is made to impinge on the target material and allow the scattering to take place by adopting diffraction pattern satisfying the Brags law condition ($n\lambda=2d\sin\theta$) where θ is the Brags angle, λ is the wave length of the X ray radiation, d is the internal planar spacing. The photograph of the Residual stress machine used is shown in Fig 1. More details may be referred from the literature [13]

Fig.1 X-ray Testing Machine

In this experiment the tests were done for different Ψ angles (Ψ is the angle between plane normal and surface normal) 2θ plane shafts are measured and a plot $\Delta 2\theta$ vs $\Delta \sin^2\Psi$ is plotted. Depending on the nature and magnitude of the x ray intensity levels, the strain is measured as Δd , the stress is calculated based on the following equation.

$$\sigma = \frac{-E \cos\theta}{1+\nu} \frac{\pi}{180} \frac{\Delta 2\theta}{\Delta \sin^2\Psi} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where σ = stress in MPa

E = Young’s modulus of the material under investigation

ν = Poisson’s ratio.

$\frac{\Delta 2\theta}{\Delta \sin^2\Psi}$ = Slope measured from the plot of 2θ Vs $\Delta \sin^2\Psi$ obtained from the experiment.

3. Results and Discussions

The test samples have been designated as shown in the Table 3.1 according to the sample descriptions provided in the same table. The section size of the casting used has the thickness of 24 mm.

Table 3.1 Sample description and designation

Sl.No	Sample Description	Sample Identification
1	Mild steel cold rolled	MS
2	NiHard4	NH4
3	High Chromium Iron	HiCr
4	High Chromium Manganese Iron 5% Mn	HiCrMn5

5	High Chromium Manganese Iron 10%Mn	HiCrMn10
6	High Chromium Manganese Iron 15% Mn	HiCrMn15

3.1 Composition

The Chemical Composition analysed are provided in the Table 3.2 It is observed from Table 3.2 that the chemical composition of the samples analysed are meeting the specifications of the standard grades in respect of HiCr and NH4, whereas the other three compositions are pertaining to the castings made in the laboratory by induction melting route.

Table 3.2 Composition of the test samples analysed Chemical Composition

Sl No		C	Mn	Si	Cv	Ni	Mo
1	MS	0.158	0.58	0.22	-	-	-
2	NH4	3.1	0.56	1.58	9.2	5.2	0.2
3	HiCr	2.90	0.58	0.75	16.8	0.4	1.35
4	HiCr 5 Mn	2.22	5.53	1.68	17.16	1.08	1.23
5	HiCr 10 Mn	2.68	10.32	1.41	17.92	0.93	1.12
6	HiCr 15 Mn	2.78	15.42	1.27	18.17	0.80	1.33

The chemical composition of the sample analysed are shown in table 3.2 it may be noticed that the components determined are meeting the standard data of the materials used

3.2 Hardness and Metallurgical data

The hardness (HRC) retained austenite and carbide volume data in respect of the test samples determined are listed in Table 3.2 the hardness measured for the test samples are in line with the typical values given in the literature.

Table 3.3 Hardness, RA and CV

Sl No	Sample designation	Retained Austinet RA	coefficient values CV	Hardness			
				Before Erosion test		After Erosion test	
				HRC	BHN	HRC	BHN
1	MS				130		160
2	NH4	65	14	49.5	468	51.0	486
3	HiCr	10	30	61.0	642	62.0	658
4	HiCr 5 Mn	52	26	59.0	613	60.0	627
5	HiCr 10 Mn	57	24.5	54.0	534	55.0	552
6	HiCr 15 Mn	62	23	50.0	469	51.0	486

The surface hardness is the essential phenomena of the metallic materials and the possibility of using the material in different industries depends on the degree of hardness. The surface hardness significantly affects the fatigue performance of materials and shows its resistance to crack initiation. Table 3.2 compares the surface hardness of the samples, it is clearly seen that the surface hardness before erosion is around 130 BHN, which has increased up to 160 BHN for MS. Moreover, the hardness of NH4 and HiCr have increased to 486 and 658 BHN after erosion, respectively. Thus, the hardness has increased by approximately 81%, 96% and 97% after erosion for MS, NH4 and HiCr, respectively compared to un eroded once. In addition, for the HiCr 5Mn, HiCr 10Mn and HiCr 15Mn samples the Hardness increased by 98%, 95% and 96% respectively over the test samples before erosion. The hardness of HiCr 5Mn sample is higher than that of the HiCr 10Mn and HiCr15Mn, but it is lower than HiCr sample. The reason for this trend may be due to hardness profile matrix structure obtained [14]. From Table 3.3 it is evident that the hardness measured on the erosion profiles are much higher compared to the values obtained before erosion. These are on the expected lines in view of the fact the samples get work hardened after erosion due to the plastics deformation involved. A further RA and CV value shown in table 3.3 ably supported the hardness values.

Higher RA and lower CV results in reduction in hardness as seen for the NH4. The HiCr show RA of 12 and CV 30, but the hardness is higher because of the mixture of chromium carbide and martensite matrix. In case of HiCr 15Mn samples, it shows lower hardness, higher RA and lower CV %, whereas HiCr5Mn samples revels highest hardness, lower RA and higher CV. The hardness of HiCr 10Mn lies in between HiCr5Mn and HiCr15Mn samples. The MS sample has been considered for reference purposes only.

3.3 Erosion loss

The material removal owing to erosion phenomenon is an account of striking of particles on the target layer. Further the erosion mainly depends upon the materials type, its composition, hardness, surface condition, abrasive type, its volume, impact angle, velocity, etc Especially the mechanical properties of these samples following erosion shows a noticeable change in respect of temperature, and other erosion impact parameter, strongly influenced by the erosion rate [15]. In spite of the complexity of the process, the single impact of a eroding particle on the surface can be understood approximately like an indentation process with different impact angles between the particle direction and the surface. If this impact angle is 90° than the results shows high rate of erosion for brittle materials such as NH4 , HiCr etc the layer producing lateral cracks within the interface. with higher compressive residual stresses impede the penetration of the particle into the layer, the cracks will be stopped inside the layer and the erosion rate is lowered for the samples with higher hardness value. At small impact angles strong shear stress components occur in the layer leading to more vertical cracks through the layer. It is known that Now compressive residual stresses induces crack propagation and controls the erosion rate and subsequently the erosion rate drops. The complex-effects of residual stresses on the erosion rate demand with great care from

the point of enhancing the erosion of parts whether residual stresses are favourable or not depends on a large number of parameters and factors of the real erosion process, and a reliable prediction may be possible by doing so. The erosion loss test data results conducted on NH4, High Chromium irons, High Chromium manganese irons, are provided in the Fig 2. Along with data from MS samples considered for comparison purpose, the data reveals a good relation among erosion, hardness with microstructured features. It may be recalled from the literature [16, 17] that for a ductile material highest erosion loss occurs at shallow angle (45° Impact angle) and for brittle materials, the maximum erosion loss is for 90° Impact angle.

The erosion data of HiCr & NH4 are typical of the phenomena occurring for brittle materials whereas HiCr Mn samples coming under combination of the brittle ductile categories as the highest erosion values obtained is at 90° and for HiCrMn samples, the erosion loss does not show steep drop in values and hence showing the ductile behaviour.

From the Fig 2 on erosion loss Vs Impact angle, the following observations are made

- (I) For MS, the erosion has taken place at 45° impact angle and least at normal impact angle (90°)
- (II) The NH4 and HiCr samples show highest erosion losses at 90° impact angle with lower erosion losses at 15° impact angle.
- (III) The HiCrMn family samples show similar erosion trends observed for HiCr/NH4 up at 45° and decrease marginally less 90° impact angle.

The hardness value and the erosion data get correlated and they are in line with the work reported by other researchers [18, 19]

Fig 2 Erosion Loss

3.4 Residual stress

Fig 3 Residual Stress

Residual stress gets reduced during the manufacturing process of a material, or it may accumulate in a structure over many years in operation. In either case, this stress may have a serious negative effect on a product's quality, durability and lifetime. The accurate measurement of residual stress is an important factor as per the quality control process and helps to predict the service lifetime of products based on the RS values and other associated parameters. Fig 3 shows the comparative results of RS induced at the surface of the samples. The residual Stress values before and after erosion are provided in Fig 3. It is clearly seen that the RS value of MS sample are compressive type and for HiCr and NH4 samples, the stress development is compressive type.

Work reported by Luo, C., et al. [20] on the Surface Properties and Cavitation Erosion Resistance of cast iron is reported in the work of laser-cavitated areas with higher hardness that could induce higher compressive stress compared to unleased areas. In the present work, a higher compressive stress area was obtained in the exposed area, thus showing a correlation to the RS levels.

Damage tolerance coating, erosion performance, and residual stress development in WC-CoCr samples reveal higher compressive stress and improved cavitation performance, as studied by Tommi Varis et al. [21] In this work, a good correlation was established between residual stress, cavitation, and RS buildup in casting. Andrew et al. [22] have investigated the interdependence of residual stress in samples made by the HVOF process. The coating has revealed good adherence to the substrate with good mechanical integration and shows a high level of residual stress, which establishes the current study RS levels.

The following are some of the observations made on RS measurements.

- The RS of HiCr is the highest while it increased further following the erosion process with 35 % improvement in RS in hardness values compared to MS increases in erosion resistance by 48% and 97% .

- The HiCrMn samples in respect of RS are showing similar pattern before and after erosion. The RS values decreased with increase in manganese content by 6%,8%, and 4% RS after the erosion compared to un-eroded samples.
- The RS has shown the least value among NH4 and HiCr samples both before and after erosion process is affected. By 96% and 97% in hardness and 20% ,5% in RS respectively after erosion

The values in respect of RS and their trends obtained are showing the similar pattern reported in the literature [13, 15] and in well coherence with their findings.

3.5 Light Microscopic Feature

The light micrographs pertaining to the samples listed in Table 3.1 are shown in Fig 4 to 9 respectively, Fig 4 pertaining to MS reveals ferrite grains in perlite matrix. The grains are very well distributed in the **perlite** matrix with equal axial types.

Fig 4 MS

Fig 5 NH4

Fig 6 HiCr

The microstructure pertaining to Ni hard 4 shown in Fig 5 reveal near eutectic carbides in a matrix of martensite of $(Cr_3Fe)_7C_3$. It is quite hard, revealing discontinuous carbide network and possessing Rockwell hardness of 49.5 in the C scale. The RA content measured is 65% and high hardness with the presence of eutectic carbides makes the surface suitable for wear resistance application. In Fig 6, the microstructure of HiCr exhibits long carbides (rod like) structure in martensitic matrix a predominant. [23] The light micrographs of HiCr, captured at a magnification of 500 \times , is presented in Fig 7. In the microstructure of HiCr iron, predominantly primarily carbides of varied sizes including hexagon type are observed in a predominantly austenite matrix. Notably, these carbides are distributed randomly within the matrix.

Fig 7 HiCrMn5

Fig 8 HiCrMn10

Fig 9 HiCrMn15

The light micrographs depicted in Fig 7 to 9 displays HiCr5Mn, HiCr10Mn, and HiCr15Mn at magnifications of 500×. The HiCr 5Mn has yielded RA of 52%, CV of 26% and hence the hardness value obtained is 59 HRC before and 60 HRC after erosion test. HiCr10Mn, with added 10% manganese, reveals long carbides with hyper-eutectic hexagonal carbides in the austenitic matrix of 57% of RA and CV of 24.5%. The measured before and after erosion test are 54.0 and 55.0 respectively. HiCr15Mn, with 15% manganese addition reveals long carbides with hyper-eutectic of bigger size carbides in the austenitic matrix (62%). The hardness measured is 50.0 and 51.0 HRC before and after Erosion test. These micrographs provide insights into erosion phenomena. The morphological features of carbides, including size, distribution, and matrices, are crucial in determining the properties of HiCr5Mn, HiCr10Mn, and HiCr50Mn. The microstructure plays a significant role in shaping the characteristics of the HiCr family, as indicated by literature reports. [13, 15, 24, 25]. Thus in summary the erosion data obtained get very good backing from the hardness, residual stress and microstructure features. Further this type of work has hardly been reported in the literature by considering these parameters and hence forms first of its kind in this sphere of work.

4. Conclusions

Based on the comparison of the results of various tests viz., hardness, erosion and residual stress for mild steel, NH₄, and high chromium materials, the following points emerge

1. The high nickel, high chromium iron exhibits good promise as an erosion-resistant material among the samples studied.
2. It is clear that hardness, retained austenite, and carbide shape all have a significant impact on the material and its influence on erosion loss.
3. The current study primarily responsible for the variations in stress levels on the composition and matrix transformations that occur in this class of materials.
4. It is seen that HiCr having higher Cr and Ni responds to high hardness, lesser erosion loss and including high compressive stress.

Thus, HiCr with high compressive stress as such may be suitable for wear resistance application; on the other hand, HiCrMn samples with different levels of Mn would serve as a matrix with improved toughness and moderate erosion resistance properties..

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